

To Observe the Functional Changes in Pulmonary Systems among Patients With CKD Over a Period of Six Months**Padmini Sirkanungo¹, Ashim Kumar Mahali², Abhijit Taraphder³**¹Assistant Professor, MGM Medical College Superspecialty Hospital, Indore²Assistant Professor, Department of Nephrology, KIMS, BBSR³Head, Department of Nephrology, Apollo Gleneagles Hospital, Kolkata

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Padmini Sirkanungo

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background & Methods:** The aim of the study is to observe the functional changes (obstructive or restrictive) in pulmonary systems among patients with CKD over a period of six months. Detailed clinical history and clinical examination of all patients fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. CBC, Serum Creatinine, USG of whole abdomen and pelvis (Size, structural abnormality of kidney etc.)**Results:** Majority of the cases were from stage 3 of CKD i.e.63.5% at baseline and 52.6% after 6 months. Proportion of cases from stage 4 were 25.4% at baseline and 42.4% after 6 months.**Conclusion:** Chest x ray was normal at baseline and after 6 months, 5 patients i.e. 4.2% had bilateral mild pleural effusion. Epworth daytime sleepiness risk assessment revealed that proportion of high-grade cases were 16.1% at baseline that increased to 35.6%. Proportion of cases from low grade were 83.9% that are decreased to 64.4% after 6 months. The difference in the proportion of cases in high grade and intermediate grade was statistically significant(<0.05). Epworth daytime sleepiness risk assessment revealed that proportion of high-grade cases were 16.1% at baseline that increased to 35.6%. Proportion of cases from low grade were 83.9% that are decreased to 64.4% after 6 months. The difference in the proportion of cases in high grade and intermediate grade was statistically significant(<0.05).**Keywords:** pulmonary, parenchymal, airway, vascular and CKD.**Study Design:** Observational Study.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is emerging to be an important chronic disease globally. One reason is the rapidly increasing worldwide incidence of diabetes [1] and hypertension. In India, given its population >1 billion, the rising incidence of CKD is likely to pose major problems for both healthcare and the economy in future years. Indeed, it has been recently estimated that the age-adjusted incidence rate of ESRD in India to be 229 per million population (pmp) [2], and >100,000 new patients enter renal replacement programs annually in India. On the other hand, because of scarce resources, only 10% of the Indian ESRD patients receive any renal replacement therapy (RRT). [3] The lack of community-based screening programs has led to patients being detected with CKD at an advanced stage. It is possible that early detection of kidney disease through community-based screening programs might have an impact on this problem through earlier intervention.

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) encompasses a spectrum of different pathophysiological processes associated with abnormal kidney function and

progressive decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR). [4] CKD has become a major cause of morbidity and mortality. In the 2015 Global Burden of Disease Study, kidney disease was the 12th most common cause of death and CKD ranked as the 17th leading cause of morbidity worldwide. [5]

CKD is already established as an important chronic disease globally. One reason is the rapidly increasing incidence of diabetes and hypertension worldwide. [6] In India, given its population >1.3 billion, the rising incidence of CKD is likely to pose major problems for both healthcare and the economy in future years. Indeed, it has been recently estimated that the age-adjusted incidence rate of ESRD in India to be 229 per million population (pmp), and >100,000 new patients enter renal replacement programs annually in India. [7]

Material and Methods

All selected patients in the time frame of the study were enrolled. Minimum cases to be studied were around 118. The purpose of the study is to evaluate proportion of different changes taking places in

pulmonary systems like parenchymal, airway, vascular and serosal changes among patients with CKD. As the variables are many and we can't have a single anticipated proportion to estimate the sample size, we consider anticipated proportion as 50% to get the maximum of the minimum sample size.

Detailed clinical history and clinical examination of all patients fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria. CBC, Serum Creatinine, USG of whole abdomen and pelvis (Size, structural abnormality of kidney etc.) Chest X ray PA view (To see any structural changes in chest) Pulse oximeter (To monitor oxygen saturation) Pulmonary function test (Spirometry) (To evaluate functional status of the lungs either restrictive or obstructive)

Inclusion Criteria

- Outpatient with chronic kidney disease having informed consent with the following routine clinical investigation.
- Age > 18 years

Exclusion Criteria

The following are the exclusion criteria for the study.

- Patient known respiratory disease like COPD, Bronchial asthma.
- Known ILD (Interstitial Lung Disease) secondary to primary disease.
- Known connective tissue disorder.
- Patient having previous pulmonary tuberculosis.
- Patient having pulmonary infection within last 3 month for which admitted in the hospital.
- Patient having cardiac surgery.

Result

Table 1: Distribution according to gender

		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	80	67.8
	Female	38	32.2
	Total	118	100.0

In our study, majority of the subjects were male i.e. 80(67.8%) and remaining were females 38(32.2%)

Table 2: Distribution according BMI grades

		Frequency	Percent
BMI grade	Normal	36	30.5
	Overweight	78	66.1
	Obese	4	3.4
	Total	118	100.0

Prevalence of obesity in our study was 3.4% and that of overweight was 66.1%

Table 3: CKD stages at baseline and after 6 months

		Baseline		After 6 months	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
STAGE	2	10	8.5	2	1.7
	3a	26	22.0	23	19.5
	3b	49	41.5	39	33.1
	4	30	25.4	50	42.4
	5	3	2.5	4	3.4
	Total	118	100.0	118	100.0

Chi square-11.7, p-0.0084(>0.05), Significant

Majority of the cases were from stage 3 of CKD i.e.63.5% at baseline and 52.6% after 6 months. Proportion of cases from stage 4 were 25.4% at baseline and 42.4% after 6 months.

Table 4: Chest x ray and sputum culture at baseline and after 6 months

		Baseline		After 6 months		Chi square test	p
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent		
CXR	Normal	118	100.0	113	95.8	2.73	0.09 (>0.05) Not significant
	Bilateral mild pleural effusion	0	0	5	4.2		
Sputum C/S	Negative	118	100.0	118	100.0	--	--

Chest x ray was normal at baseline and after 6 months, 5 patients i.e. 4.2% had bilateral mild pleural effusion ($p>0.05$). Sputum cultures were negative at baseline as well as after 6 months.

Table 5: Epworth Sleepiness Risk grade at baseline and after 6 months for day time sleepiness

		Baseline		After 6 months	
		Frequency	Percent	Frequency	Percent
Epworth Sleepiness Risk grade	High	19	16.1	42	35.6
	Low	99	83.9	76	64.4
	Total	118	100.0	118	100.0

Chi square-11.69, $p=0.0007(<0.05)$, Significant

Epworth sleepiness risk assessment for day time sleepiness revealed that proportion of high-grade cases were 16.1% at baseline that increased to 35.6%. Proportion of cases from low grade were 83.9% that are decreased to 64.4% after 6 months. The difference in the proportion of cases in high grade and low grade was statistically significant (<0.05).

Discussion

Trudzinski FC et al reported that the majority of all patients (60.6%) were male, and the mean \pm SD age was 65.0 ± 8.4 years.

Navaneethan SD et al reported mean age as 62.1 ± 0.3 years and 46.7% were males.

Ashima Sharma in their study found that the average age was 45.8 ± 10.0 years; 64% were males.

Berger and coworkers et al [8] reported a 4% (14 of 436) incidence of uremic pleural effusions in chronic renal failure which is almost similar to our findings whereas Jarratt and Sahn et al reported a 16% (16 of 100) incidence of pleural effusion secondary to uremia which is higher than our findings because in their study patients were on dialysis. [9]

ForniOgna V et al [10] reported prevalence of moderate to severe OSA in his population was 56%, and 31% of the subjects had severe OSA (with a clear indication for treatment), but only a small proportion of all OSA patients (19%) had been previously diagnosed and even less (10%) were treated.

The largest epidemiologic study in this field reported an OSA prevalence of 23.6% using Berlin's Questionnaire [11] which may have

underestimated the prevalence of this condition considering its poor performance in the hemodialysis population. The other trials were small studies with selective recruitment of symptomatic patients, [12] except for two recent studies performed in USA and Canada in patients with different degrees of chronic kidney disease attending outpatient nephrology clinics. Both studies recruited a subgroup of 75 patients on intermittent hemodialysis, investigated by home polysomnography in the American protocol and by overnight respiratory monitoring in Canada. [13]

Our results are in line with the reported prevalence of moderate to severe OSA of 57% in the Canadian study and above the 25.7% prevalence of severe OSA observed in the US study. The lower prevalence in the latter may be due to a less sensitive sensor.

Conclusion

Prevalence of obesity in our study was 3.4% and that of overweight was 66.1%. Chest x ray was normal at baseline and after 6 months, 5 patients i.e. 4.2% had bilateral mild pleural effusion. Epworth daytime sleepiness risk assessment revealed that proportion of high-grade cases were 16.1% at baseline that increased to 35.6%. Proportion of cases from low grade were 83.9% that are decreased to 64.4% after 6 months. The difference in the proportion of cases in high grade and intermediate grade was statistically significant (<0.05). Epworth daytime sleepiness risk assessment revealed that proportion of high-grade cases were 16.1% at baseline that increased to 35.6%. Proportion of cases from low grade were 83.9% that are decreased to 64.4% after 6 months. The difference in the proportion of cases in high

grade and intermediate grade was statistically significant(<0.05).

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